

21ST CENTURY FOOD
INNOVATIONS - HEALTH - COLOURS

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21ST CENTURY FOOD

INTRODUCTION

1

Contemporary, diverse dietary trends, often emphasizing '*flexitarianism*' and/or the 'planetary diet', are intended not only to maintain consumer health and well-being, but also to align with sustainable life patterns and promote the preservation of natural environmental values. Therefore, food products are increasingly being viewed in the context of sustainable development, and they are designated 'sustainable' when it '*possesses certain characteristics: It must be ecologically healthy, economically viable, socially equitable, and culturally diverse*'.

From a sustainability perspective, one might get the impression that the current leading dietary trend is '*leading a healthy life in harmony with nature*', and that modern consumers are required not only to raise their environmental awareness but also to understand that following current, top-tier dietary trends should not conflict with real nutritional needs. Consumers aim to consciously choose food products from both local and global producers, taking into account production technologies and preservation methods.

21ST CENTURY FOOD

Current Challenges

2

The enormous scientific and technological progress during the Industrial Revolution era, especially in the last few decades, brought not only numerous innovative food processing methods but also many innovative food preservation technologies, recalling new physical concepts. This is associated with the emergence of non-thermal food preservation methods, primarily aimed at ensuring microbiological safety and extending shelf life while maintaining the high quality of food products. Among non-thermal food preservation methods, one can indicate the ‘*Cold Plasma*’ (CP) method, as a potentially important decontamination technique. Notable is also the pulsed electric field (PEF) method, which uses short pulses of high-intensity electric fields (from 15-80 kV/cm) generated over an extremely short period. There is also the ‘*Pulsed Light*’ (PL) technology, which uses intense and short light pulses (100-400 μ s) across a broad spectral range (200-1110 nm). Such non-thermal methods are used not only for food preservation but also to alter the nutritional, sensory, and physicochemical properties of a targeted food product. Following topical references, the use of ‘Pulsed Light’ can compensate for the time of fruit exposure to sunlight (...) or change the amount of vitamins, nutrients, etc. contained in a given product. For example, it has been observed that in mushrooms exposed to ‘Pulsed Light’ the amount of vitamin D₂ increased. For figs, changes in color appear, which coincide with the amount of polyphenolic compounds contained in figs.

It should be emphasized that the methods recalled above can affect the product's surface or the micrometric layer directly beneath.

In such a context, **High Pressure Preservation (HPP)** – also known as **Cold Pasteurization** or **Pascalization** - holds a special position. It can act immediately throughout the entire product, both ‘liquids’ (beverages) and ‘solids’, from meats and fish to jams. The benefits of HPP have already been recognized by numerous producers and consumers worldwide: it is now a huge multi-billion dollar market.

21ST CENTURY FOOD

Notably, HPP is an ‘extremely’ environmentally friendly method, with no pollution and requiring a few times less energy than the standard thermal pasteurization. It provides food products with high microbiological safety and preserves the immunological, nutritional, and sensory properties of fresh products, including texture & colors. All of these coherently link ‘freshness’ and the extended shelf life. This meets the expectations of logistics, retailers, and consumers, which until now seemed impossible to reconcile.

3

The aforementioned methods of preserving and processing food products meet the needs of modern consumers, who generally seek minimally processed foods with characteristics similar to fresh products. The current ‘naturalness trend’, or ‘elevated convenience’, understood as the need for ‘an increased level of convenience’, as well as other food trends generally favoring vegetarianism and veganism, demonstrate that consumers are guided when purchasing food by the benefits resulting from the need to improve physical and emotional well-being, or the need to reduce the likelihood of developing lifestyle diseases. One response to these consumer needs is the so-called ‘clean label’ or a symbol of a blue drop with a white leaf, which assures consumers that a given food product is free from ingredients such as artificial colors, preservatives, and flavor enhancers.

Modern, intelligent technologies also offer many effective solutions for the marketing and promotion of food products, a stage where visual and sensory aspects are of great importance. The latest ‘Instagram-able’ trend, which enhances and highlights food's visual and flavor qualities, aligns with these needs. According to Meticulous Research, the most impressive food color of the year 2022 is Veri Peri purple, also described as a ‘*dynamic blue with an invigorating purple-red undertone*’. Veri Peri¹, while incredibly charming, can be found in anthocyanidins, plant pigments found in all berries, such as cherries, raspberries, strawberries, blackberries, quinces, grapes, and red cabbage. These water-soluble plant pigments give fruits and flowers their red, blue, or violet colors, and their color depends on environmental pH, the presence of other pigments such as flavones and carotenoids, and the presence of metals. The color of grape wines, their flavor, and aroma also depend on the presence of anthocyanins and flavonoids. In red wine production, grape juice remains in contact

¹ <https://www.pantone.com/color-of-the-year-2022>

21ST CENTURY FOOD

with the fruit skin long enough for anthocyanins, flavanols, and catechins to enter solution. Pigments, or biologically active plant phytochemicals, help fight disease and maintain the body's energy balance.

It should be noted, however, that the color of many modern food products is not necessarily related to the properties of the biologically active ingredients they contain, as it often comes from natural dyes added to foods not so much to enhance their nutritional and visual value as to enhance their purchasing value. Similarly, many food products are enriched with vitamins and nutrients to impart health-promoting properties that align with consumer purchasing preferences. When considering food products from a marketing perspective, it's important to note that, in addition to the 'clean label', attributes such as 'health and ethics' are crucial, prioritizing nutritional value, healthiness, and food safety, as well as environmental friendliness and sustainable food processing and preservation.

The expectations and tastes of 21st century consumers, focused on the visual and sensory qualities of food products, align with food trends related to sustainable development, which, in turn, are inherently consistent with a system that recognizes the interdependence and equivalence of nature, society, and the economy. Currently, it is important to strive to live in harmony with nature and achieve healthy well-being, while limiting the exploitation of natural resources and fully caring for the natural environment.

Ayurveda has promoted an approach to life and health that provides consumers with 'complete physical health, peace of mind, and spiritual well-being' for years. Although the Ayurvedic concept of healing dates back to over 5,000 BC, its ideas focused on 'achieving and maintaining balance in body, mind, and the external environment' remain relevant. Over time, the general perception of the world, as well as lifestyles, have clearly changed, largely due to enormous advances in science and technology and socio-economic transformations. However, one might get the impression that the need to live in harmony with nature, or to maintain health through conscious eating, remains constant. Of particular interest here is the Ayurvedic concept of nutrition, which teaches that allowing one's psychophysical constitution to become imbalanced can lead to a loss of happiness and health, as the body then ceases to coexist in harmony with nature. To achieve this, it is necessary to determine one's

21ST CENTURY FOOD

constitutional type, i.e., to recognize one's strengths and weaknesses, mental and emotional predispositions, and to establish a proper diet based on the quality of food and the color of individual foods. Food color indicates whether a given product is suitable for a given individual. Importantly, Ayurveda, viewing proper nutrition as one of the main environmental factors contributing to good health, considers nutrition an integral part of the art of healing, and views health as harmony with nature.

5

For centuries, Ayurvedic sages, through trial and error, have developed a system for defining and assigning specific food colors (green, yellow, red, white, or brown), physiological and anatomical characteristics, and unique psychological and spiritual traits. They have also correlated specific lifestyles and diets with each food color, and described therapies that minimize susceptibility to certain diseases. Therefore, Ayurveda teaches that everybody needs an individualized set of foods, adapted to their constitution. In proper nutrition, in addition to the appropriate proportions of ingredients and foods, the colour of the food and its associated nutritional values and flavors are crucial.

The contemporary approach to nutrition is fundamentally not based on meeting individual consumer needs, as what's currently important is food products that are 'safe for everyone'. Knowledge of major nutritional trends and the ability to understand food labels are crucial, and consumers expect to be knowledgeable about structural ecology and social ecology. Knowledge of preventive health care is also crucial, with diet, nutrition, and a healthy lifestyle as pillars of living in harmony with nature. This approach aligns perfectly with the practices of the Ayurvedic healing system, because although the realities of life have changed significantly, the saying remains true: *'Food is life. If consumed properly, it prolongs youth and increases longevity. Incorrectly consumed food produces toxins and, in effect, takes away life.'*

In conclusion, it can be said that learning about the mutual correlations between the way of eating, lifestyle, physiognomy, and health inclinations of the body seems to be interesting both from the point of view of understanding the Ayurvedic healing system and a contemporary approach to the latest scientific reports considering current nutritional trends, aimed at 'Improving Immunity, Eyesight, Figure, Well-Being', discussed, among others, by the authors of the work Food Compass, November 2021.

21ST CENTURY FOOD

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